

Application to Structural Use of Glass Fiber Reinforced Concrete

M. Mashima¹⁾, T. Mise¹⁾, K. Okada²⁾

- 1) Department of Civil Engineering, Osaka City University, Sugimoto, Sumiyoshi-ku, Osaka 558, Japan
- 2) Department of Civil Engineering, Kyoto University, Yoshida-honmachi, Sakyo-ku, Kyoto 606, Japan

ABSTRACT

The paper describes two series of test results about glass fiber reinforced concrete which consists of ordinary cement concrete and reinforcing glass fiber to study the properties both of fresh and hardened state and to improve the placing method. In the first case, the slump tests and the Vee-Bee tests of fresh concrete and the compressive, splitting tensile and flexural tests of hardened concrete are carried out to obtain the referring data for the design of mixing proportion. Also, fracture toughness is evaluated by the results of the flexural tests with a stiff loading machine. The second experiments are trial of placing poor consistency concrete such as fiber reinforced concrete. The effects of trial products are discussed about the flexural test results of "compacted concrete".

INTRODUCTION

Portland cement concrete has been superior composite material and major construction material because of the high compressive strength, easy dealing without skilful experience and economics. On the other hand, this material is inferior to the tensile strength, flexural strength, impact property and fracture toughness.

Some attempts have been made in order to improve these poor characteristics. One of them is to add and disperse randomly a good many of short fiber into cementitious concrete and to be reinforced by them. This composite material is called "Fiber Reinforced Concrete" and is expected as a new composite material for structural utilization.

Although there are various kinds of reinforcing fiber, such as steel fiber, glass fiber, carbon fiber, polymer fiber and asbestos, fiber reinforced concrete has been mainly developed and studied by using steel fiber up to nowadays. Then, the interests in studying about steel fiber reinforced concrete are practical utilization, structural design method and other practical items. However, glass fiber reinforced cement, which is made of cement paste or cement mortar and glass fiber has been mainly studied by means of the spray method. Glass fiber has superior characteristics of durability against salt and high tensile ability, therefore, practical application of glass fiber reinforced

concrete, which consists of cement mortar, coarse aggregate and glass fiber, is capable for structural members of construction.

This paper describes the results of three experimental program for application of glass fiber reinforced concrete.

First, the consistency or workability of fresh concrete, the mechanical properties of hardened concrete and their mutual relationships are studied experimentally. Second, the flexural behaviors after failure are evaluated by introducing the concept of toughness index (T.I.). Lastly, the statically compacted concrete is produced by way of trial as a placing example of glass fiber reinforced concrete with poor consistency and the effect of compaction is studied from the view point of mechanical properties.

USING MATERIALS AND MIXING OF CONCRETE

The ordinary or high early strength portland cement is used. Aggregates are sea sand for fine aggregate and crushed stone of maximum size 15mm for coarse aggregate through the experiments. The reinforcing glass fiber is an alkali resistance glass fiber of chopped strand in 24mm length which consists of 204 monofilaments of 13 μ m in diameter.

The all of glass fiber reinforced concrete is mixed with the tilting drum mixer to prevent loosing and chopping of glass fiber.

PROPERTIES OF FRESH AND HARDENED GLASS FIBER REINFORCED CONCRETE

Experimental Program

The decrease in workability or consistency is generally recognized for fiber reinforced concrete. This observation is obviously rheological and can not be neglected in the case of deciding the mix proportion. For example, the method of increasing the fine aggregate ratio or the water cement ratio is used usually but the reinforcing effects of glass fiber may be cancelled occasionally in this way. Therefore, this series of experimental program is objected to study the influence of the mixing factors including glass fiber content on fresh and hardened concrete.

The consistency or workability of fresh concrete is measured by means both of the slump test and the Vee-Bee test which are specified the general testing methods for quality control.

The mechanical properties of hardened concrete are indicated by three kinds of strength, the compressive strength of ϕ 10x20cm cylinder, the splitting tensile strength of ϕ 15x15cm cylinder and the flexural strength of 10x10x40cm prism.

The experimental factors of mixing components are the fine aggregate ratios (S/A), water cement ratios (W/C), fiber contents (V_f) and fiber length (l_f). These experimental factors and levels are shown in Table-1.

Effect of Water Cement Ratio and Fiber Content

Figure-1 shows the relationships between the slump values and the water cement ratios with the parameter of the fiber contents. The consistency is

Table-1 Experimental program

factor		level				
fine agg. ratio	S/A	0.40	0.50	0.60	0.80	
water cement ratio	W/C	0.45	0.50	0.55	0.60	0.65 0.70
fiber content	V_f (%)	0	0.2	0.6	1.0	
fiber length	l_f (mm)	12	24	37	50	

remarkably decrease by addition of even small amount of glass fiber. Also, these relationships are approximately linear and their slopes are getting gentle along with increasing the fiber contents except unreliable data written dotted line in Figure-1. This figure also presents that the consistency is getting well due to increasing the water cement ratio i.e. unit water content because the increase of the water cement ratio equals to the increase of the unit water content in case that unit the cement content is constant.

These results are observed similarly to the tendency which are linear relations between the unit water content and the consistency with some range in plain concrete. The relationships between the water cement ratio and the Vee-Bee values are shown in Figure-2. These results are similar to the results of the slump tests.

Figure-1 S_l -W/C- V_f relations

Figure-2 VB-W/C- V_f relations

Figure-3 σ_c - V_f -W/C relations

Figure-4 σ_t, σ_{MOR} - V_f -W/C relations

It becomes experimentally clear that the consistency of fresh glass fiber reinforced concrete is decreasing along with increasing amount of glass fiber. But the consistency is getting well with increasing the water cement ratio or the unit water content.

The relationships among the water cement ratios, fiber contents and compressive strengths are shown in Figure-3. There is a marked lowering in the compressive strength with increasing the fiber contents. This is because of void included into glass fiber and shearing characteristics of glass fiber.

However, the tensile and flexural strength is obviously increasing by the effect of glass fiber in Figure-4. In special, the effect of flexural strength becomes even stronger, but is not influenced by the change of water cement ratio so much. The relations between the tensile strength and the fiber content are parallel each other in spite of the change of the water cement ratio. Therefore, the effect of tensile strength is additional to the strength of plain concrete or matrix concrete.

Effect of Fine Aggregate Ratio

It is generally recognized that there is a peak value of the slump value against the fine aggregate ratio in plain concrete which means ordinary cement concrete including no reinforcing fiber. This peak value is called an optimum fine aggregate ratio and the important factor for the design of mix proportion. The optimum fine aggregate ratio is observed similarly in both the slump test and the Vee-Bee test.

However, the peak value which is the optimum fine aggregate ratio is not presented so clearly and is only recognized in a small in Figure-4. The slump values are very insensitive for the change of the fine aggregate ratio. And the effect of the fine aggregate ratio on the Vee-Bee values does not show any tendencies with accuracy as shown in Figure-5. These figures also present that glass fiber has an important effect upon the slump and Vee-Bee values. There are the peak values in the slump value or the constant values in the Vee-Bee value in the region of 0.6-0.8 of the fine aggregate ratio.

Figure-7 shows the relationships between the compressive strength and the fine aggregate ratio and there is the maximum compressive strength against the fine aggregate ratio. The fine aggregate ratio for the maximum compressive strength almost agree with the peak value or the constant value of the consistency/fine aggregate relation. These values are considered as the quasi-optimum fine aggregate ratio for any fiber content. By the way, the fall of compressive strength of plain concrete and low fiber content concrete in Figure-7 indicates so large. This is due to segregation of matrix concrete and is supposed from the results of slump test.

Figure-8 shows the relationships between the tensile and/or flexural strength and the fine aggregate ratio. The tensile strength is increasing along with increasing the fine aggregate ratio. This is reasonable corresponding to the results of customary studies. The flexural strength which is presented as an ultimate state (modulus of rupture) is not influenced so much about the fine aggregate ratio. But it is obvious that the tensile and flexural strength is increased by adding fiber. This is also additional effect on the strength of plain concrete.

Effect of Fiber Length

The slump value is decreasing only slightly in case of using longer fiber as shown in Figure-9. Also the compressive, tensile and flexural strength is increasing a little but not so influenced except fiber length 12mm in Figure-11 and 12. As an aspect ratio of glass fiber cannot be defined so clearly, this concept is not practical factor for explaining the concrete properties. Fiber reinforced concrete of 12mm glass fiber length is smaller in the flexural strength than other lengths. This is owed that the critical fixed length is 5-10mm from the results of the pull out tests of glass fiber.

Figure-5 Sl-S/A- V_f relations

Figure VB-S/A- V_f relations

Figure-7 σ_c -S/A- V_f relations

Figure-8 σ_t, σ_{MOR} -S/A- V_f relations

Figure-9 Sl- l_f - V_f relations

Figure-10 VB- l_f - V_f relations

Glass fiber is chopped at the fracture plane and is not drawn out almost. Therefore, the fixed length of glass fiber is shorter than or equal to using length, then influence of fiber length is not appeared clearly.

EVALUATION OF FRACTURE TOUGHNESS

The other main object of adding fiber into cementitious concrete material is to

Figure-11 $\sigma_c - V_f - l_f$ relation

Figure-12 $\sigma_t, \sigma_{MOR} - V_f - l_f$ relations

Figure-13 Typical load-deflection curve

Figure-14 Concept of T.I.

Figure-15 Increase of T.I. with increase in fiber contents

improve the ductility or fracture toughness which is able to be defined as an enveloping area stress-strain or load-deformation curve. Therefore, it is necessary to obtain the relation even where the failure has been beginning and bearing load has been decreasing. For this purpose, the flexural tests are carried out using the stiff testing machine which is raised stiffness by connecting the upper and lower cross head of the universal loading machine and load-deflection curve is electrically recorded with a X-Y recorder.

Typical load-deflection curves of plain concrete and fiber reinforced concrete are shown in Figure-13. The curves show the difference of falling branch among the change of fiber content i.e. the flexural bearing load becomes to be falling down gradually with increasing fiber content after failure has

Figure-16 Compacting effects in flexural strength

Table-2 Experimental program of compacted concrete

factor	level			
compacting load (MPa)	0	0.1	0.3	0.5
fiber content V_f (%)	1	2	3	
compacting method	release	continous		

Figure-17 Amount of dehydration water

Table-3 Density of compacted concrete

fiber content (%)	compacting stress (MPa)			
	0	0.1	0.3	0.5
		rels. cont.	rels. cont.	rels. cont.
plain concrete	2.371		2.394 2.421	2.385 2.431
	357	—	364 414	389 396
	353		398 423	379 419
1	2.193		2.263 2.312	2.285 2.317
	180	—	279 335	269 311
	136		324 320	262 338
2		2.281 2.286	2.225 2.243	2.258 2.254
	—	269 268	208 306	248 256
		247 275	190 320	295 280
3			2.135 2.044	—
	—	—	144 125	
			145	

been occurred. Figure-14 indicates toughness index(T.I.) which is the evaluation of falling degree of the loading capacity. T.I. is defined as the ratio between enveloping area of load-deflection curve to failure point and area of including after failure as shown in Figure-15. This figure presents remarkably linear increase in T.I. with increasing the glass fiber content.

PROPERTIES OF COMPACTED GLASS FIBER REINFORCED CONCRETE

Experimental Program

In previous section, the consistency of fresh concrete, the mechanical properties of hardened concrete and their relations are studied experimentally and are discussed about the results.

The decline of the consistency cannot be avoided experimentally and is evident rheologically. Then, it is difficult to improve the workability of glass fiber reinforced concrete in design of mixing proportion. This series of experiments is a trial of using glass fiber reinforced concrete of poor consistency and adding more amount of glass fiber into concrete by the pre-mixing method. The trial products which are called "compacted concrete" are placed and compacted with external vibration and statical compacting load, and the compacting effect is studied from the mechanical properties.

Experimental factors are taken up about the glass fiber contents, static compacting loads and compacting methods. These details are shown in Table-2. There are two kinds of compacting method, the release method and the continuous method. The former is the method to release immediately the compacting load after arriving the necessary load and the later is the to maintain the compacting load for 24 hours.

Results and Discussions

Figure-16 shows the flexural test results in this series of experiments. The flexural strength are increased by compaction on both plain concrete and fiber reinforced concrete and this is the effect of compaction in placing concrete. These phenomena are mainly caused by the following process: (1) consolidation of fresh concrete (2) drainage of free water (3) increase in the strength.

The increasing rate of the flexural strength of plain concrete is not so large as compared with fiber reinforced concrete in spite of increase in drainage water in Figure-17. The water cement ratio becomes below 0.4 at compacting stress over 0.3MPa from the calculation by amount of drainage water but the increase of the flexural strength is not so much. This difference is due to drain cement particles accompanied with dehydration.

It is very difficult to place glass fiber reinforced concrete with usual method over the fiber content 1% because of zero slump. If placed, a lot of air void remains in hardened concrete and the strength is decreased. These facts which are not presented in this paper are confirmed in the previous experiments.

However, it becomes capable to use more amount of glass fiber content 1% and it is not observed the decrease of strength in "compacted concrete" of this experimental series. Besides, the flexural strength is increasing with increasing both the compacting force and fiber content up to 2%. The flexural strength of fiber reinforced concrete with 3% glass fiber falls down as the compacting effect cannot overcome to bulky effect supposed amount of drainage water in Figure-17.

There is an upper limit for the compacting stress which is nearly 0.3MPa and drainage water approaches to constant value regardless the fiber content. These effects are not influenced so much by compacting method, the release method or the continuous method as shown in Figure-16.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors wish to express their deep gratitude to M.Eng. Tomokazu IDEGUCHI of Osaka Municipal Office for cooperation of experiments and discussions.